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ARCHITECTURAL PRINCIPLES OF PLANNING RURAL AREAS OF UZBEKISTAN

ANNOTATION

In the article, the villages are more ancient places of residence than cities, the emergence of villages, the social division of labor is connected with the development of farming culture, the study of rural areas pays special attention to the natural conditions of the area where they are located, and the climatic conditions, terrain, water of the places. and information on the importance of soil resources, flora, etc. is provided.

Key words: village, territory, neotectonics, farming, recreation, recreation, sanatorium, alternative, streets, squares.

O‘ZBEKISTON QISHLOQ AHOLI HUDUDLARINI REJALASHTIRISHNING ARXITEKTURAVIY TAMOYILLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada qishloqlar shaharlarga qaraganda aholi yashash joyining qadimdan shakllanganligi, qishloqlarning vujudga kelishi, ijtimoiy mehnat taqsimoti dehqonchilik madaniyati rivojlanishi bilan bog‘liqligi, qishloq joylarni o‘rganishda ular joylashgan hududning tabiiy sharoitiga alohida e‘tibor berilishligi va joylarning iqlim sharoiti, reliefi, suv va tuproq resurslari, o‘simlik dunyosi kabilarning muhimligi haqida ma‘lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: qishloq, hudud, neotektonik, dehqonchilik, rekreatsiya, oromgoh, sihatgoh, muqobil, ko‘chalar, maydonlar.

АРХИТЕКТУРНЫЕ ПРИНЦИПЫ ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ СЕЛЬСКОЙ МЕСТНОСТИ РАЙОНЫ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье показано, что деревни являются более древними местами проживания, чем города, возникновение деревень, общественное разделение труда связано с развитием культуры земледелия, при изучении сельских территорий особое внимание уделяется природным условиям местности, где они расположены, и климатическим условиям, рельефу местности., вода из тех мест. также предоставляется информация о важности почвенных ресурсов, флоры и т.д.

Ключевые слова: деревня, территория, неотектоника, сельское хозяйство, рекреация, оздоровление, санаторий, альтернатива, улицы, площади.

Rural areas are areas outside cities and towns that contain land regularly used for agriculture and permanent settlements (territories).

Villages are a more ancient form of settlement than cities. The emergence of villages is associated with the development of the social division of labor in the agricultural culture. Agriculture was initially carried out using natural water flows, and later developed on the basis of irrigation structures (dams, canals, etc.) and means. Thus, a community, territorial unity of people, and settled settlements appeared. As a result of the separation of agriculture from animal husbandry and the development of crafts and trade on this basis, the next important stage of the social and territorial division of labor began [1, 2, 3].

When studying rural areas, special attention should be paid to the natural conditions of the area in which they are located. In particular, the climatic conditions, relief, water and soil resources, and plant life of the area are of great importance.

Thus, villages are more closely related to natural conditions than cities. In addition, local building materials such as sand, gravel, lime, stone, etc. also play an important role in shaping the appearance of the village (Figure 1).

Figure 1. General view of the villages of Uzbekistan.

The basis for the formation and development of villages is the economic sectors. In this regard, villages are divided into three categories:

- specialized in agriculture;
- not specialized in agriculture;
- mixed villages.

In turn, villages specializing in agriculture are formed by villages engaged in gardening and viticulture, irrigated agriculture, and livestock breeding. The ability of these agricultural sectors to "create a village" also varies. Relatively large villages arise in regions with developed irrigated agriculture, and the settlements of the population engaged in livestock breeding are not very large.

Mixed-type villages arose on the basis of the development of the above two sectors or, as a rule, agriculture and related industrial enterprises.

The demographic potential of such villages can be relatively large. Therefore, the size of villages is determined by the function they perform. This is one of the most important laws of the geography of settlements.

The service sectors for the population, for example, education, healthcare, are organized in a hierarchical manner in rural areas. The lowest level of the education or healthcare systems is located in small villages, and as villages grow larger, the facilities related to these sectors organized in them also grow larger. For example, in some of the largest villages, a college or academic lyceum, a large library, a hospital, specialized shops, a bank, and supermarkets are organized (Figure 2).

Figure 2. 1-club (youth center), 2-neighborhood center, 3-shopping center, 4-school, 5-kindergarten, 6-QVP, 7-heating supply, 8-bathroom, 9-10-11-12-low-rise residential buildings (three, four and five rooms), 13-14-15-16- medium-rise residential buildings, 17-production area.

Villages are also of great importance in the development of recreation and tourism. There are many places in our republic with fresh air, shade, and beautiful scenery. In particular, various camps and sanatoriums have been established in villages along streams and springs. At the same time, there are great opportunities for the development of local, religious, agrotourism and ecotourism in rural areas [4, 5].

Various shrines, caves and waterfalls, magnificent mountain or oasis landscapes, national folk games, ceremonies and weddings, food and costumes are also of great tourist importance. In particular, agrotourism plays a key role in the development of local and regional economies.

When studying rural settlements, they are first classified. In this regard, villages are divided into three main classes: small villages (population up to 1,000 people), medium-sized (1,000-3,000 people), and large (3,000 people and more) villages.

Special studies make this grouping more precise. For example, villages can be divided into the following classes according to their size:

- small villages - population up to 500 people;
- small villages - 500-1000 people;
- medium villages - 1000-3000 people;
- large villages - 3000-5000 people;
- large villages - more than 5000 people.

The division of rural settlements into the above groups is not accidental; of course, the specialization and integration of rural economies at different stages, their educational, trade, healthcare, financial institutions, production and social infrastructure branches are different.

The size of villages, as previously noted, depends on the industry they specialize in. In turn, the large or small population of villages affects the location of services and the service sector.

The geographical study of rural settlements, in addition to grouping them by size, also involves dividing them into separate types according to the function they perform. The division of villages into three main functions was mentioned earlier. At the same time, villages can also be divided into groups that serve as ordinary and rural citizen gatherings, and sometimes as centers of rural districts.

In the healthcare system, the territorial characteristics of rural medical centers (RMPs) are also studied, such as their density, the number of people they serve, and their area of influence - radius.

The village is usually considered a passive and weaker settlement compared to the city in socio-economic development. The multifunctionality of cities, their size, strong innovation, investment and infrastructure potential, diversified and highly developed economy, wide opportunities for the population to live, study, receive treatment and work, and their influence ensure that they play a leading role in regional, socio-economic systems or complexes.

The village is to some extent subordinate to the city, providing it with agricultural raw materials, clean air and water for its population, and labor for its economy. The city, in turn, supplies the village with qualified personnel, machinery, equipment, mineral fertilizers, building materials, and modern service for agriculture.

Indeed, in our conditions, attention to the village means attention to the people. Consequently, if the village is prosperous, the Motherland will be prosperous. Because the culture of our country, the mentality of our people formed over the centuries, our values depend primarily on the origin and development of villages. Even today, agriculture is one of the main macroeconomic sectors in the formation of the national and regional economy. Until recently, the majority of the population of the republic, that is, 2/3, lived in villages.

966 rural settlements (RS) across the republic have been granted township status. In particular, 196 in Fergana region, 118 in Kashkadarya, 109 in Namangan region, and 107 in Surkhandarya have been transformed into towns. As a result, there have been dramatic changes in the structure of settlements in the republic and the level of urbanization in the regions.

Typically, when granting the status of a village to a town, it is advisable to take into account the following:

- the population must be at least more than 2,000 people;
- the rate of population growth and its employment indicators;
- the geographical location of the village;
- the function performed by the village;
- the state of housing construction, improvement;
- transport and social infrastructure;
- industry and consumer services;
- the development of the service sector;
- the investment climate and the presence of joint ventures;
- the education and healthcare system;
- the provision of a master plan, project documentation, etc.

The architectural planning project of rural settlements is a comprehensive urban planning document that serves as the basis for determining the development prospects of each settlement. This project is developed for the entire territory of a rural community or a rural economic enterprise, including rural settlements, production areas, engineering structures, arable land, etc. Such a document does not allow the construction of random objects whose socio-economic necessity has not been confirmed.

The task of the architectural planning project for rural areas is to determine the comprehensive development of the territory of the rural community, the feasibility of functional zoning, as well as to stimulate the interconnected development of all settlements that form the settlement system, to ensure the full functioning of farms and provide farmers and their family members with comfortable conditions, and to provide farms with engineering, social and cultural service infrastructure.

In the architectural planning project for rural areas, the calculation of the territories required for the construction of residential, industrial, and cultural and household facilities is carried out based on a study of the modern demographic structure of the population and population growth rates for the calculated period.

Rural areas are designed and divided into 3 main parts.

1. Residential area;
2. Production area;
3. Agricultural fields;

The residential area includes:

- residential buildings;
- public buildings;
- streets, squares, parking lots and green areas.

The production area includes:

- production areas not belonging to the agricultural production unit, production buildings belonging to the agricultural production unit, warehouses, garages for agricultural machinery, workshops, livestock and poultry farms, agricultural product processing workshops and production of household goods.

Agricultural land includes:

- Cropland, orchards, vineyards, mulberry orchards, forests, pastures and hayfields.

The architectural planning of rural areas includes the following:

1. Economic analysis and development of proposals for the general development of each settlement and rural settlement for the next 5-7 years and the future development of the territory for the next 10-15 years;
2. Design calculations of the general growth of the population for the next 5-7 years and the future growth of the population for the next 10-15 years;
3. Proposals for employment of the rural population, the creation of additional jobs;

4. Determination of the volume of work to be carried out on the improvement of the engineering infrastructure of the territory of the rural settlement, the implementation of water supply and sewage, gas and heat supply, electricity and energy systems;

5. Development of housing construction;

6. Organization of social infrastructure, networks of schools and preschool educational institutions;

7. Formation of a cultural and social service system;

8. Organization of medical services;

9. Development of proposals for the organization of networks of recreational facilities and improving the aesthetic quality of the territory;

10. Improvement of transport and passenger communications;

11. Development of proposals for the rational use of land to improve the ecological situation, protect historical and cultural monuments, valuable landscapes and water resources.

The project of architectural and design organization of the territory of the village citizens' meeting. – A comprehensive urban planning document for the village citizens' meeting, this document solves the fundamental issues of urban planning.

The project structure of rural settlements, the comprehensive development of the territory of the village citizens' meeting, taking into account the correctness of functional design, improving the architectural appearance, improving the living conditions of the population, developing agricultural production, environmental protection, comprehensive use of natural material and human resources, organizing the formation of recreational services and developing existing ones. The perspective development of rural settlements and the next 15-20 years are analyzed.

The sequence of development of urban planning documents for rural settlements.

Formation of inter-farm settlement. Rural settlements, being an element of the settlement system, are formed on the basis of the existing territorial structure:

- administrative district;
- rural citizens' assembly;
- farming association and agro-firm;
- farm;
- rural settlement;

A rational system of settlement should correspond to the prospects for the development of production and the development of agricultural production. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the formation of social production, engineering-transport and other infrastructures, as well as cultural-household, recreational and labor relations within the boundaries of the rural citizens' assembly.

Main tasks.

Determination of the future development of agricultural production facilities in accordance with the land development project and the forecast of socio-economic development of the agricultural enterprise, the location and planning of the foundations of these facilities;

- reconstruction of the established location within the farm in accordance with the territorial organization of agricultural production;

- determination of the population of the agricultural enterprise, including the projected number of residents in each settlement;

- organization of a system of cultural and household services on the territory of the agricultural enterprise;

- determination of the necessary volumes for housing and production construction for citizens and the places where they will be located;

- organization of transport and pedestrian communications within the farm;

- development of proposals for engineering support, improvement and landscape formation of settlements within the agricultural enterprise;

- development of principled schemes for planning settlements regardless of population size;

- development of proposals for environmental protection, protection and use of natural, historical and cultural monuments.

The solution of the listed tasks should be carried out on an alternative basis, the criterion for their evaluation is the achievement of a high socio-economic standard of living of the rural population with minimal damage to nature and other resources.

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